

Purposes and Structures of Sarcasm: A Pragmatic Study

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 22, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 26, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Sarcasm, Illocutionary Sarcasm, Propositional Sarcasm, Evaluation, Sophistication, Political Debates, Brexit</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5602029</p>	<p><i>This study explores sarcasm pragmatically in British Prime Minister Boris Johnson's Brexit debates. This work is chosen to focus on this topic because it is vital in modern political discourse. The study's goals are figuring out the pragmatic structure of sarcasm in politician speech interaction, i.e. identifying the most common pragmatic structures of sarcasm in political debate. Studying its effect as a negative or positive act in political debates and showing if there are distinct patterns. In light of the above goals the following hypothesis are set: 1) Brexit debates uses sarcasm and Sarcastic utterances with certain pragmatic structures and specific accommodations. 2) Sarcasm is used in political debates with a sense of humour avoiding direct aggressiveness, besides a negative attitude is a fatal weapon. 3) In political debates, sarcasm serves both the speaker and the situation surrounds him. Several methods are to test these hypotheses' validity and examine the literature on Sarcasm's definitions, types, and theories, etc. gaining a broad understanding of the phenomenon; In Boris Johnson's political debates; examining the political sarcastic situations. The debates were examined using a model created for this purpose involving Camp's (2012) classification for pragmatic purposes of sarcasm and Attrado's (2001) classification for the pragmatic purposes of sarcasm. The study concludes that some pragmatic structures e.g. illocutionary sarcasm and propositional sarcasm are more commonly used to convey the speaker's intentions, as well as that sarcasm can be used to convey both a negative message and positive one.</i></p>

Introduction

1.1 Pragmatics in General

Generally, pragmatics is to some extent a modern field of linguistic inquiry, which has its origin in the philosophy of language. Its philosophical roots belong to the philosophy of the 1930s, particularly the work of Charles Morris, Rudolf Carnap, and Charles Peirce. According to Huang (2007, p. 2), semiotics is divided into three parts: syntax, semantics, and pragmatics. Syntax is concerned with the formal relationship between two signs, semantics with the relationship between signs and their meaning, and pragmatics with the relationship between signals and their users and interpreters. Thus, syntax is the most abstract, pragmatics is the least abstract, and semantics is in between. As a result, syntax is a source of information for semantics, whereas semantics itself is a source of information for pragmatics.

1.2 Sarcasm

Sarcasm is one aspect of figurative language, which is commonly used in oral conversations. Some people believe that sarcasm only used for mocking or being rude to others. Katyayan (2019) define sarcasm as an attempt to make a sharp or bitter comment in order to fulfil any of the three purposes, as wit, as whimper, or as evasion (p. 169). Sarcastic statements generally do not mean themselves literally but convey implicit meaning often as contrast of their actual meaning. Katyayan declared the negativity and indirectness of sarcasm to serve specific purposes. According to Shaw (1976), sarcasm is a type of irony, bitter and often harsh derision. Sarcasm, for him, is always personal, always mocking, and always intended to hurt (p. 241). A written sarcasm example can be found in Byron's comment on another English poet, Robert Southey, which is filled with sarcastic remarks such as:

(1) "He first sank to the bottom—like his work, But soon rose to the surface-like himself Because all corrupted things float like corks, Because of their own rottenness"

Byron criticises Southey underestimating his work indicating that it is insignificant "He first sank to the bottom-like his work," Then he moves to criticise Southey personally referring to him as a shallow person "But soon rose to the surface-like himself". The aggressiveness, insulting and disdain are obvious and manifested via sarcastic expressions. Dews et al. (1995), point out that sarcasm, combined with devices such as jocularly, hyperbole, rhetorical questions, and understatement, are linguistic constructions that can help produce irony (p. 1574). This means that such types of means are strategies by which irony is expressed. Fowler (1991) says, "the essence of sarcasm is the intention of giving pain by ironical words or other bitter words" (p. 78). Abrams (1981)

defines sarcasm as a form of irony that sometimes used as equivalent for all irony forms, but it differs in the exaggeration of the speakers' voice (intonation) (p.136). From Abrams definition, sarcasm seems to have another basic property in addition to intention, which is the intonation (tone).

Regarding all these opinions, a definition for sarcasm can be drawn; Sarcasm is an indirect and expressive speech act in a form of verbal irony or sometimes a behavioural irony in which the speaker has a frank intention to express his (mostly) negative attitude towards interlocutors (hurting or criticising, etc...). Sarcasm can be found spoken or rarely written. It has its special form and patterns related to some extra-linguistic features (when spoken), precise intonation.

1.3 Sarcasm and other aspects

1.3.1 Sarcasm and irony:

Broadly speaking, typically, an ironic remark creates a tension over what is said and what is supposed to be expressed. This difference is frequently the outcome of an utterance's pragmatic perception. Thus, it is critical not to accept a sarcastic statement literally, as the pragmatic interpretation contains the actual message.

At the beginning of the 19th century, the expression 'irony' begins to adopt various meanings that range from recently developed distinctions of irony such as philosophical irony, world irony, tragic irony and cosmic irony (Li, 2008, p. 3). Furthermore, Muecke (1982) maintains that the word 'irony' never appears in English till 1502 and does not come into general literary use till the 18th century like in the rest of Europe, the concept of irony improve so slowly in England (p. 16). Irony is clarified as saying reverse of what someone means as saying something to mean another, as blaming to praise and praising to blame. As a rhetorical device, Valstos (1991) assumes that irony becomes furthermore tricky when its riddle is interrelated throughout a text (p. 21). Cruse (2006) mentions Irony is a type of figures of speech wherein the actual intent of a phrase is generally the complete antithesis of the literal interpretation, like when someone says:

(2) You have been a tremendous help!

Addressing one whose actions have just precipitated a catastrophe (p. 90). The literal meaning of an ironic statement frequently mirrors someone else's words or assumed views and is intended to criticise or mock... Here, Cruse maintains that, in order to achieve sarcastic expression one must be ironic. For him, sarcasm is one of the purposes of irony. In literature, there are three forms of irony:

1. Verbal irony occurs when a character says something that isn't true to their feelings or intent. Sarcasm is the purpose of irony, to ridicule. To urge others to make assertions that may be debated, a person feigns ignorance.
2. Situational irony occurs when expectations and reality diverge. An example of situational irony is a fire station on fire.
3. Dramatic irony occurs when the characters know more than the viewers. The characters' actions have a different meaning than the audience's, which adds to the drama. Tragic irony is utilised in tragedies. (Web source 1)

It can be said that irony is the bigger umbrella where all other senses of opposite and mockery lies. Whereas sarcasm is more directed more specified and harsher. Another difference is that a person is ironic when he contradict himself, his words or words to actions, while sarcastic utterances happens when words uttered contradict actual feeling, attitudes or aspects.

1.3.2 Sarcasm and satire:

Satire is a kind of wit intended to criticise human vices or errors, frequently via the use of exaggeration, understatement, sarcasm, and irony. Nowadays, satirists most frequently employ this type of comedy to reveal political errors or societal deficiencies in ordinary life, perhaps with the intention of encouraging change. Web source 1: What Is Satire? How to Use Satire in Literature, Pop Culture, and Politics—Plus Tips on Using Satire in Writing. (Websource 1)

The term "satire" derives from the Latin word "Satur," which means "well-fed," and was used in the phrase "lanxsatura," which translates as "a plate brimming with various types of fruit." Though these terms appear to be at odds with the modern concept of satire, they were employed by ancient Roman critics and authors to refer to what we now refer to as satire, including what is often regarded as satire's literary origin: Aristophanes's Old Comedy. In the sixteenth century, the term "satire" entered the English language. Aristophanes, an ancient Greek poet, authored *Lysistrata* in 411 BC. In this satirical comedy, *Lysistrata* urges women to forgo intimacy from males to persuade them to stop the Peloponnesian War. (Ibid.)

Satire in Literature is 'societal critique'. Exaggeration, irony, and other tactics are used to mock a leader, a social habit or tradition, or any other prominent social figure or practise. Satire has been used to remark on anything. The first political cartoons appeared in 18th-century England. Political satire is still essential today. Satire serves in two political streams:

1. Political Cartoons: These can be printed or online. A political cartoon often has one huge panel with a sketch that exaggerates the physical attributes of an elected politician or other noteworthy figure and shows a situation that makes a scathing political statement.

2. Political Stunts: Some comedians have gone beyond sarcastic jokes on TV to do elaborate political satire pranks. In his 2018 television show *Who Is America?* Comedian Sacha Baron Cohen disguised himself to interview politicians and catch them in moments of hilarity and hypocrisy. (Ibid)

It is obvious that sarcasm is more generalized rather than specific, i.e. occurs in more varied situations than satire does and words on different social levels. Satire in modern sense is specified in political field, giving possible solutions, criticizing, mocking and judging political issues from both politicians and citizens.

2. Pragmatic Approach to Sarcasm:

This section presents the pragmatic theoretical background that explains and explores the sarcastic phenomenon occurrence. First, the pragmatic function of sarcasm will be detected, and then the functions behind using such sarcastic utterances are explored.

2.1 Camp's classification:

Camp (2012) proposes pragmatic categorisation of sarcasm and divides it into four types: propositional sarcasm, lexical sarcasm, 'like'-prefixed sarcasm, and illocutionary sarcasm (p.588). Each of the constructs are based on the idea that sarcasm works by reversing context, As a result, each type either rejects something or purports something. In her study, Camp (2012) tried to come up with this subcategories of sarcasm relating it to three previous theories, Sarcasm, according to semanticism, is stored in logical form by an operator that 'inverts' the literal meaning of the word or sentence it applies to. Right-wing expressivist denies that sarcasm or verbal irony has any meaning. Rather, it draws attention to a discrepancy between a "dissociative attitudes" regarding some elements of this discrepancy. She also argue that. These two competitors place sarcasm on opposite ends of a scale. At the same time, they both: argue that sarcasm only works one way by means of inverted meaning overtly. This leaves many sarcastic situations unable to be explained. A good explanation needs a deeper grasp of sarcasm, but also broader meaning. She relates two types (propositional sarcasm and lexical sarcasm) to this normative scale. Traditional sarcasm delivers an implicature that is the opposite of a statement that would be communicated by an honest remark (Camp 2012, p.598). Implicature theorists supplement their analysis with two additional clauses: a presupposition that someone else has endorsed the content she makes as if to express, and an implicature that the speaker does not approve of this content. Similarly, a semanticist may assert that a felicitous application of sarcasm assumes that the embedded content has been approved, and thus sarcasm outputs a two-pronged value: the embedded content's truth-conditional opposite and a negative assessment of that embedded content. (Ibid., p. 599)

She finally came out to conclude that all three approaches examine 'what is stated' in truth-conditional terms. Daring to express and encourage evaluative views are part of the definition of sarcasm. Slurs and moral phrases are examples of genuine, direct, and literal communication (Ibid.,p.599).

2.1.1 The Pragmatic Structures of Sarcasm:

Camp (2012) proposed four pragmatic structures for sarcasm based on here conclusion from the expressivist, semanticism and implicature theorist.

1. Propositional sarcasm: Propositional sarcasm is the most direct of the four forms of sarcasm discussed (ibid). In addition, the idea of sarcasm is founded on Yule's (2010) based on presupposition and entailment principles (p.25). Thus, propositional sarcasm focuses on the sarcastic comment. Presenting the opposite of a fact, Like: "He's a good pal." (Camp, 2012: 607).

To understand this sarcastic statement, the speaker should give a type of confirmation, signalling the opposite to the true utterance. Therefore, both semantic and lexically centred pragmatic processes will interpret this as sarcastic. The statement "he is a good friend" connotes a circumstance where one would think the talk is about a good friend, but the speaker really implies the opposite (ibid.,p.607). An example of proposed sarcasm from the TV programme *Sherlock*:

3) Anderson: *Rachel means vengeance*. She may be attempting to communicate.

Thank you for your input.

The caustic comment made by Sherlock to irritate Anderson; contrary to what the literal utterance's meaning Anderson wants to say and it is obvious that Sherlock is clever and knows that already (Camp, 2012: 608).

2. Lexical sarcasm: Sarcastic utterances are generally identified by a vocabulary. It's true that the speaker is engaged in illocutionary power here, but the lexically focused pragmatic procedures imply the opposite notion (Camp, 2012, p.611). The frequent use of terms like 'brilliant', 'genius', 'magnificent', 'thrilled', etc... It is also connected to lexical sarcasm. Sarcastic phrases convey the exact opposite connotation. For example, "Wonderful idea". Sarcasm will imply the other extremity of the spectrum, i.e. highly terrible (ibid: 613). Also, an utterance might have negative value although its surface meaning is good. As in:

4) *If you can come up with one more half-baked, insignificant proposal, you will be guaranteed tenure.*

The word 'tenure' is used sarcastically as a reward for poor performance (Camp, 2012, p. 45).

3. Like -prefixed sarcasm: This category includes declarative statements and is guided by conventional meaning as well as pragmatic procedures. The use of sarcastic like that creates the sense of reversing what follows emphasises that the speaker is refusing what follows.

5) *I haven't talked to John in weeks.*

In this comment, the speaker is caustic, claiming she did not converse with John (ibid: 19).

6) *That's a great concept.*

The caustic utterance (6) indicates the opposite of the next remark. The concept is neither brilliant nor unimportant (Camp, 2012: 613).

4. Illocutionary sarcasm: According to Camp, (2012) illocutionary sarcasm is the complete illocutionary conduct directed by a lawful utterance of the linked discourse. Also, evaluative sentiments like pity. Illocutionary sarcasm is distinguished by its implied appreciation (p. 618).

For example, when someone is leaving a location and another person behind him screams the door, the speaker will be amazed, inserting the following statement:

7) *I appreciate your help.*

The most effective sarcasm is the one that contrasts the actual scenario with the sarcastic statement. Any illocutionary speech, such as expressions, queries, commands, and optative, can be used sarcastically:

8) *Could I tempt you to eat just one more slice of pie?(To someone who has just finished the pie).*
(Hawthorne/Camp, 2008, p.3)

2.2 Attrado's Classification:

Sarcasm is a complex and subtle speaking act; the listener must decipher implied meanings. Sarcasm is a form of linguistic irony used to show one's ability to "manipulate" language. A speaker implies a word (Attrado, 2000, p.68).

Sarcasm, according to Camp (2012), is an evaluative attitude that can be negative or positive. Then she adds that all sarcastic structures are inverted or reversed, explicitly or implicitly. She assigned a function to each interlaced structure. Sarcasm, a form of comedy, also has a worldwide influence.

2.2.1 The Pragmatic Purposes of Sarcasm:

According to Attrado's (2001), sarcasm is classified as an interplay between comedy and irony (p.172). Sarcasm provides six functions according to him: sophistication, evaluation tool, politeness tool, a persuasive aspect, retract ability, and group affiliation tool.

1- Sophistication: Sarcasm is a verbal game that shows a speaker's mastery of the English language. The speaker can regulate his emotional state by manipulating his words Attardo (2001, p.183). Therefore, sarcasm is a clever and subtle way of expressing oneself especially in politics creating a less aggressive environment than expressing intended meaning directly. Because the listener must first understand, the speaker's suggested meaning before continuing the dialogue. Films also utilise sarcasm to produce comic effects. In such cases, the speaker delivers a comment that contradicts the intended intention. The difference between implicit and explicit meaning in speech may also assist generate humour in specific contexts, according to Dews et al (1995, p.154). Omitting some phrases also creates a void between the words and the inferred meaning (Ibid, p.185). However, there are occasions in which sarcasm does not derive from humour, and vice versa, but mostly it has a humorous effect.

2- Evaluation: Sperber and Wilson (1981), on the other hand, argue that when evaluative sarcastic phrases are used to introduce criticism, the negative consequences of criticism are disguised while the good benefits of praise are amplified (p.133). Using civility in one's discourse can help to reduce the negative impact of unfavourable emotions. In order to avoid looking foolish, many resort to utilising sarcastic remarks.

3- Politeness: Sarcasm may also be used to perform politeness. It is seen as less harmful than outright hostility in direct verbal acts. Dews and Winner (1995) suggest that sarcasm reduces the threat of intentional meanings (p.13). Barbe (1995) adds that employing sarcasm might help a speaker avoid causing a rupture by not being overtly insulting the addressee. The speaker's politeness reduces the impact of unfavourable feelings. Sarcasm is thus a face-saving tactic (p.90).

4- Persuasive aspects: The role of sarcasm in persuasive communication is critical. Researchers argue that irony possesses a number of unique characteristics that make it an excellent tool for persuasion, most notably the ability to emphasize the contrast between expectation and reality. Sarcasm works by establishing unstructured intellectual groups that encourage audiences to view themselves as "masterminds" in accepting the values to which sarcasm alludes inadvertently. Researchers illustrate this in a variety of applied contexts (e.g., advertisements, personal arguments, political debates, intellectual discussions, and literature) and argue that contemporary cognitive and social psychology research provides conclusive proof behind why sarcasm is so frequently used in persuasive communication (Gibbs, R. W., Jr., & Izzett, C. D., 2005, p.135).

5- Retract ability: Sarcasm as a retract ability is used to express things in such a manner that the speaker may avoid being made responsible for improper behaviour. Carston (2002) asserts that a speaker can avoid any consequences associated with expressing his feelings directly. This characteristic enables the speaker to approach his remark with an open mind. However, this use of sarcasm is quite unusual, as it necessitates a highly specific context (p. 23-25).

6- Group Affiliation: Sarcasm, as a kind of group membership, enables the speaker to establish both insider and outsider status. It establishes the group's allegiance. Sarcasm has a dual role in this instance. To begin, sarcasm may be used to foster intragroup cohesion. Second, it can be used to express negative judgements about people

and to exclude them from a group. Thus, it demonstrates whether someone adheres to the group's values (Myers-Roy, 1981: 412).

3. Methodology:

The qualitative and quantitative approach are both followed in the current study by presenting a theoretical background qualitatively and calculating the analysed data results quantitatively. The data selected from Boris Johnson's Brexit debates as streamed on ITV from The House of Commons. The speaker is Boris Johnson, the addressee are British people and MPs, and the context is negotiating the Brexit deal; its privileges and drawbacks. The setting (time and place) is before the parliament passes the Brexit deal in the House of Commons. The data selected lasted for an hour and a half basically arguing the effects of England withdrawal from the European Union on the country and the consequences of the failure of that deal.

The model adopted for this study is based on Camp's (2012) classification for the pragmatic structures of sarcasm including (illocutionary sarcasm, propositional sarcasm, lexical sarcasm and like-prefixed sarcasm) and Attrado's (2001) classification for the pragmatic functions of sarcasm including only (evaluation, persuasion and sophistication).

4. Analysis, Findings and discussion:

4.1 Analysis of Data

4.1.1 Data description:

The following extracts are extracted from a debate occurred in 19 December 2019. In the House of Commons. Between Boris as the conservatives' leader and Corbyn as the labour's leader. They clash after the queen's speech supporting the conservative political vision about Brexit (British exit out of the European Union). Eleven sarcastic situations are found in the debate under scrutiny, two of them will be analysed in detail and the rest will be analysed as showed in table (1).

Extract (1): The following extract includes part of the questions imposed by a female member of parliament (a Labour member) to Boris Johnson (Prime Minister). The Lady urges and demands Boris' government to be stricter with anyone who breaks the law and brings disorder to their country, she infolds that Boris' government is not doing what should be done. Boris replays to her question saying that security, safety of people is his government's goal, and no one is able to be better than he is.

Illustrative extract (1):

MP (Lab): *"to impose tougher sentences on the most serious offenders now."*

Boris: *"if the Honourable Lady opposite actually wants to contest the need for tougher sentences for serious offenders, I'm happy to hear!"*

Analysis of extract (1):

Pragmatic Structure of Sarcasm:

Illocutionary Sarcasm:

The speaker commits himself to the utterance that suggests disparity with the situation; an evaluative attitude appears when the speaker clarifies the disparity between the MP's speech and the actual policy of her party towards the issue discussed. The speaker rejects to replay until she delivers her suggestions. Instead, he inserts a locutionary positive proposition that implies contrary and that positivity depends on the conditional sentence. Boris wants to state that *"to contest the need for tougher sentences for serious offenders,"* which is his initial political concern and which is not for her party, then the MP's speech contradicts their actions and views. He moves on to say, *"I'm happy to hear!"* where he pretends this act but sarcastically reflects their inability to deliver what she is demanding.

The Pragmatic function of sarcasm:

Evaluation:

The sarcastic utterance delivered functions as an evaluative scale reflecting criticism for a specific group of people; the Labour party and their policy. This evaluation eliminates the idea imposed by the MP from the general policy adopted by the party's vision.

Sarcastic utterance here exposes the speaker's repulsive attitude towards the opposite party in general, their perception, and the conception delivered by their MP, which initially contradicts their perception.

Overall, the illocutionary structure of sarcasm helped in generating sarcastic sense indirectly signifying offend mood.

Extract (2): in the following extract, Boris is praising the newspaper that supports his campaign and praises his follower a conservative member who was praised in 'The Daily Telegraph'. Boris is addressing the speaker of the house (Mr. Bercow) and MPs.

Illustrative extract:

Boris: *"if you can't believe the Daily Telegraph Mr. speaker, what can you believe!"*

Analysis of extract (2):

The pragmatic structure of sarcasm:

Illocutionary structure:

This form appears when there is disparity between the action that occurred ahead and what is said after. This disparity creates a sarcastic sense.

Boris begins with a condition addressing the speaker in particular and MPs in general. What is expected to follow in the main clause is the release of the condition; instead, he neglects such a possible release cancelling all other options. He implies that 'The Guardian', which is a newspaper that supports Labours and is mentioned earlier by Corbyn, is not to be trusted or believed in because he enclosed believe in 'The Daily telegraph' putting it in a high scale of respect and honesty.

The pragmatic function of sarcasm:

Evaluation:

The recipient of the sarcastic utterance identity is a factor that reveals whether a friendly function is adopted or the contrary. Boris here addresses his follower member and the speaker of the house (a conservative alliance). The way he structured his words presents a sense of humour.

Besides, this sarcastic utterance evokes an evaluative scale(self-evaluation). Boris gives positive credit to his followers in the party, his campaigning newspaper, and consequently, his positive points to the opposition parties and the electoral audience in general.As a result, sarcastic utterances can hold for positive sense, not only harsh negative ones.

To sum up, the illocutionary structure that includes disparity, which evokes the humour sense. Pragmatic aspect and pragmatic structures gave way to the pragmatic function behind using them, which is self-evaluation and humour.

Table 1 Pragmatic Analysis of the Purposes and Structures of Sarcasm in all Sarcastic Utterances in the Debate.

No.	extracts	Illocutionary sarcasm	Propositional sarcasm	Lexical sarcasm	Like-prefixed sarcasm	Evaluative aspect	Persuasive aspect	Sophistication
3	the leader of the Opposition a stickler as we all know for watching a Queen's speech at the right time though I don't I don't know what he has against chlorinated chicken		√			√		
4	Mr. speaker as our exchanges across these dispatch boxes come towards a close alas!			√		√		
5	so I done laid aside and they have they have forfeited the confidence of the opposition	√						√
6	I'm happy to give way if he's opposed to it he's opposed to helping struggling commuters		√			√		
7	"and I'm delighted here for sure"			√				√
8	I think it was Nicola Sturgeon	√						√

	herself who said that the referendum in 2014 was a once-in-a-generation I don't know about you Mr. speaker							
9	but I feel that the Scottish nationalists body should concentrate more on delivering all the domestic priorities and rather less on breaking up our United Kingdom	√				√		
8	it is a very interesting idea he should be I advised him to watch this face and indeed watch this space			√		√		
10	and indeed watch that space between between those Islands because what has said is not it has not fallen on deaf ears		√			√		

Table 2 Frequencies and Percentages of all Aspects of Model Occurrence.

Aspects	Illocutionary sarcasm	Propositional sarcasm	Lexical sarcasm	Like-prefixed sarcasm	Evaluation aspect	Sophistication	Persuasion aspect
Frequencies	5	3	3	0	8	3	0
Percentages	45.454%	27.272%	27.272%	0%	72.727%	27.272%	0%

4.2 Findings and Discussion:

1. Illocutionary Sarcasm

The occurrences of illocutionary sarcasm indicates higher percentages (45.454%) as shown in table (2). It ranks the first between all sarcasm structures. This is possibly because illocutionary sarcasm can reflect the speaker's attitude without any direct insult or criticism.

2. Propositional Sarcasm and Lexical Sarcasm

Propositional sarcasm and lexical sarcasm come the second as a pragmatic structure of sarcasm used in political debates (27.272%). These aspects involves reversed meaning either of a lexicon as in lexical sarcasm or to pretend the opposite as in propositional Sarcasm, which serves the speakers intention to criticise interlocutors or a specific idea.

3. Evaluation

It is a major purpose for adopting sarcasm in political discourse. It ranks the first in analysis (72.727%) of all purposes. This is because sarcasm mainly serves the speaker rationale behind using it and in political debates the speaker is after proving his point and defeating others points.

4. Sophistication

It is another purpose of sarcasm and ranked the second (27.272%) as shown in table (2). It reflects the speaker's ability to use language skilfully and adds a sense of humour to criticism, which is highly required in political debates.

5. Conclusions

Based on findings, analysis and investigation, the following conclusions can be listed as follows:

1. Unique pragmatic frameworks govern sarcasm; what is meant is revealed and interpreted contextually and situationally
2. The illocutionary and propositional pragmatic structures of sarcasm are the most frequently used pragmatic methods for delivering sarcasm in the debates analysed, which supports the first hypothesis.
3. Sarcasm is employed pragmatically for two purposes mainly: evaluative intent, and sophistication. When utilised in political debates, it is also used in everyday interactional circumstances. This fortifies partially the second hypothesis, and reject negativity of sarcasm.
4. The structures and purposes of sarcasm in the debate reflect the speaker's position and need for sarcasm, which supports the third hypothesis.

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- Web source 1: <https://www.masterclass.com/articles/learn-the-differences-between-irony-sarcasm-satire-and-paradox#what-is-irony>. Retrieved in 30 Aug 2021
- Appendix 1:** <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lunMfWDvpx4>.

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